

Notable anti-vermicial activity of polymeric ionic liquids against *Pheretima posthuma*

K. T. Prabhu Charan^a, Nallepalli Pothanagandhi^a, Kasina Manojkumar^a, Prabodh Ranjan^a,
Kari Vijayakrishna^{*a}, Akella Sivaramakrishna^a and Podili Koteswaraiah^b

^aOrganic Chemistry Division, School of Advanced Sciences,

^bBiomedical Sciences Division, School of Biosciences and Technology, VIT University, Vellore-632 014,
Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : vijayakrishna_kari@yahoo.co.in

Abstract : The aim of this study is to evaluate anti-vermicial activity of six different polymeric ionic liquids (PILs) by *in vitro* plate method. Polymer of type poly-1-vinyl-imidazolium salt possessing different counter anionic parts such as bromide and hydroxide tailored with different side chains (ethyl, butyl, pentyl) were screened for anti-vermicial activity towards Indian earth worm (*Pheretima posthuma*) in dose dependent and time dependent manner. All the tested PILs showed higher anti-vermicial activity while compared to control anti-vermicial drug (Albendazole) at same dose; however among all the PILs, those with longer alkyl chain length (ethyl, butyl, and pentyl) and hydroxide as counter anion exhibited significant activity than that of corresponding bromides and other shorter alkyl chains.

Keywords : 1-Vinylimidazole, azobisisobutyronitrile, polymeric ionic liquids, *Pheretima posthuma*, vermicial infections, vermicides.

Introduction

Vermicial infections are one of the major causes of concern in the regular health chart. Various helminthic species are known to cause severe diseases in humans and animals, some of them are lethal too^{1,2}. As per World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 1.5 billion of world populations were infected with soil transmitted helminthic infections every year. Vermicides infections are most common and widespread infections. A usual fatal disease, Helminthiasis caused by helminthic worms such as round worm and tape worm cause major part of the damage. These vermicides parasites are getting resistant to the currently available standard vermicial drugs. Room temperature ionic liquids have great impact on different fields of science as acute toxicity of ionic liquids were studied on Zebra fish³, Crustaceans⁴, Baltic Algae^{5,6}. PILs also known as poly electrolytes that possess the properties of both ionic liquids (melting point less than 100 °C, highly polar, non-volatile and inflammable⁷) and polymers. After introduction of these PILs in 1970 by Hoover⁸, they got attention in various fields of sci-

ence. The applications of PILs are expanding in different fields of science such as antibacterial brushes⁹, gene delivery vector¹⁰, anti cancerous agents¹¹, in preparation of polymersomes¹² etc. Tunable property of the PILs tailored with biologically active cations or anions can greatly influence properties of anti-vermicial ingredients. We found there is a remarkable therapeutic anti-vermicial activity of PILs compared to that of commercial drug Albendazole and some of the plant extract. In this paper, we discuss about the synthesis and anti-vermicial activities of various PILs against *Pheretima posthuma*.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

1-Vinylimidazole, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as received, 1-ethylbromide, 1-butylbromide, lithium hydroxide, acetone, ethyl-acetate, methanol, chloroform were purchased from SD-Fine Chemicals, azobisisobutyronitrile, *n*-pentyl bromide, were purchased from AVRA Chemicals. All solvents were distilled prior to usage.

Synthesis of polymeric ionic liquid :

Poly-1-vinyl-imidazole was synthesized as follows, 1-vinyl-imidazole 15 g (0.159 mol) was taken in dry Schlenk flask followed by addition of radical initiator AIBN 0.86 g (0.0053 mol) and the flask was maintained at inert atmosphere and kept for heating around 65 °C for 4 h, which leads to formation of polymerized poly-1-vinyl-imidazole¹³. Yield : 12.4 g (82.6%). The above obtained poly-1-vinyl-imidazole was dissolved in appropriate amount of methanol followed by addition of *n*-alkyl bromide and kept for heating around 65 °C for 3 h which leads to the formation of PILs of the kind poly-1-vinyl-3-alkyl-imidazolium bromides which were further precipitated in cold acetone.

Anion metathesis reaction of polymeric ionic liquid :

Poly-1-vinyl-3-alkyl-imidazolium hydroxide was synthesized by simple anion metathesis reaction between poly-1-vinyl-3-alkyl-imidazolium bromide and lithium hydroxide^{14,15}. Initially 2 g (0.0162 mol) of poly-1-vinyl-3-alkyl-imidazolium bromide was dissolved in 10 mL of methanol and 1.168 g (0.048 mol) of lithium hydroxide (were dissolved in minimum amount of water) are taken in dry round bottom flask and kept for stirring at room temperature until reaction completes. After completion of the reaction, solvents were rotor evaporated and PIL OH was extracted from chloroform, where as lithium hydroxide and lithium bromide were immiscible in ethanol. The organic extracts were evaporated and dried under vacuum to give poly-1-vinyl-3-alkyl-imidazolium hydroxide.

Anti-vermicial activity :

Indian adult earthworms, *Pheretima posthuma* were employed for screening of anti-vermicial activity of PILs.

The earthworms were collected from CMC hospital moisture soil, Vellore, India and cleaned with saline to remove all faecal matter. The anti-vermicial activity was performed according to the literature procedure with minor modifications¹⁶. Earthworms of the size 8 ± 1 cm were employed for the activity. The worms were acclimatized to the laboratory conditions before experimentation. The earthworms were divided into five groups containing five worms in each group were placed in each petriplate and four different concentrations i.e. 0.5, 2.5, 5, 10 mg/mL of PILs were employed for this activity. Each test sample (10 mL) of respective concentration was poured into each petriplate containing earthworms. The experiment was performed in triplicates to confirm the results and the mean values were taken. Earthworms after being exposed to PILs and positive control exhibited paralysis. After getting paralyzed some of the earthworms die due to high anti-vermicial activity of the test samples. The time of death of the worm was determined by transferring the worm into beaker containing hot water at 50 °C which stimulated the movements if the worm was alive. The death of the worm was confirmed when worms lose their movements followed by change in color of the worm. The percentage of paralysis and percentage of mortality were noted at different time intervals of 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90 and 120 min.

Results and discussion

Imidazolium based PILs PIL-Ethyl(ViIm)Br, PIL-Ethyl(ViIm)OH, PIL-Butyl(ViIm)Br, PIL-Butyl(ViIm)OH, PIL-Pentyl(ViIm)Br and PIL-Pentyl(ViIm)OH were prepared as per the procedure (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthetic scheme for synthesis of imidazolium based PILs with different counter anions.

For the first time, we have carried out vermicultural activities of six different imidazolium based PILs having bromide and hydroxide as counter anions.

Vermicultural activities of PILs were carried out against Indian earthworm. Vermicultural effect of the PILs was noted as a function of percentages of paralysis and percentage of mortality of earthworms at four different concentrations i.e. 0.5, 2.5, 5 and 10 mg/mL. PIL of respective concentration were poured into each petriplate containing earthworms. Some of the earthworms got paralyzed due to anti-vermicultural activity of the employed PILs. The percentage of paralysis and percentage of mortality of earthworms were noted at regular time intervals of 15, 30, 45, 60, 75, 90 and 120 min. The percentage mortality and percentage paralysis of Albendazole and ionic liquids are negligible compared to that of PILs in short span of time; this can be clearly notified in Fig. 1. The experiments were performed in triplicates.

The hydrophobicity of the imidazolium based PILs tagged with different alkyl side chains increase with the increase in alkyl chain length. PILs with the longest alkyl chain (pentyl) are observed with utmost anti-vermicultural activity compared to the rest (ethyl and butyl) and this trend can be directly correlated with their hydrophobic nature (Fig. 1). This elevated levels of hydrophobicity in PIL-Pentyl(ViIm)Br/OH PILs enhance their diffusion across the phospho-lipid bilayer of parasitic worms. But further studies are required to draw a structure activity relationship.

The mode of action of the anti-vermicultural drugs on the parasitic worms is still uncertain but a little explanation has given in literature reports till date¹⁷⁻²⁰. Oxidation of Albendazole to Albendazole sulfoxide on further oxidation gives Albendazole sulphone. Albendazole sulfoxide and Albendazole sulphone were hydrophobic. The anti-vermicultural drug Albendazole sulfoxide and Albendazole sulphone suppresses the beta tubulin polymerase enzyme that consequently leads to decrease in the uptake of glucose and exhaustion of glycogen storage eventually the parasite dies¹⁷⁻²⁰. As PILs increases hydrophobicity in surface of the earthworm as all the metabolic activities were arrested and worms were dead due to suffocation (Fig. 1). As discussed above, imidazolium based PILs may follow a similar mode of action against the parasitic worms as the standard anti-vermicultural drugs.

We have given importance in easy way of synthesis of PILs and engaging as anti-vermicultural agents, these PILs were less laborious compared to that of plant extracts (which is origin for herbal drugs). Tunable activity of PILs could be controlled by changing respective anions and alkyl side chains. Further studies can be made to explore the drug design, mechanism of action, structure-activity relationship, prosperities and consequences of employing imidazolium based PILs as anti-vermicultural drugs.

Conclusion

In this study, anti-vermicultural activity of imidazolium based PILs against Indian earthworm *Pheretima posthuma* was carried out. Paralysis of earthworms were noticed with all the six PILs that were employed for this study, even at low concentrations 0.5 mg/mL. As the *N*-alkyl

Fig. 1. (a) Mode of action of PILs through lipid bilayer. (b) % Mortality of earthworms against Albendazole, [Bmim]Br and PIL-Pentyl(ViIm)OH at 0.5 mg/mL concentration.

side chain length increased from ethyl to pentyl in both PIL-Br and PIL-OH, an increase in anti-vermicultural activity is noticed. Also, PIL-OH exhibited significant anti-vermicultural activity compared to PIL-Br. Hence, it is obvious that the anti-vermicultural activity of PILs is strongly dependent on nature of the *N*-alkyl side chain as well as counter anion. PIL-Pentyl(ViIm)OH showed highest activity than remaining PILs, standard anthelmintic drug i.e. Albendazole.

Acknowledgement

Dr. Kari thanks DST-SERB, India (Project No. SR/S1/OC-22/2012) for the financial support. Authors also thank DST-VIT-FIST for NMR, VIT-SIF for GC-MS and other instrumentation facilities.

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